

ISic4405

Small altar dedicated to Aphrodite

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Megara Hyblaea

Place of origin (modern)

Megara Iblea

Provenance

Found after the original publication of the Hellenistic temple north of the agora, in excavation of 1968 of the area of the archaic building 'k' (Megara 1), c.20 m north-east of the Hellenistic temple, in re-use in a late wall

Coordinates

37.204466, 15.181895

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Megara Hyblaea, Antiquarium di Megara Hyblaia, inventory MH C22

Physical Description

A small limestone altar, with mouldings top and bottom at the front and sides, smooth behind, and a depression in the upper surface.

Dimensions

Height 4.5 cm

Width 7.5 cm

Depth 6.6 cm

Layout

Three lines of Greek letters are incised into the front face, occupying most of the space between the mouldings, with a more or less consistent left margin and an uneven right margin

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are somewhat unevenly incised. Horizontals on alpha and eta often slope down to the left; epsilon is lunate; theta is roughly circulate with a detached horizontal bar in the centre; mu is unevenly incised, with a middle stroke which does not descend all the way.

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 3-7 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: 2-4 mm

Interlineation line 2 to 3: 0-2 mm

Text

1. Μητριου
2. ανάθεμα
3. Ἀφροδίτη

Apparatus

Text of Tréziny 2018

Translation (en)

Dedication of (?) to Aphrodite

Commentary

The first line is not entirely clear in (the publication provides a drawing only, no photograph). The curved trace after 'eta' is compatible with a lunate sigma (compare small lunate epsilon in line 2) and the female name Μηστρία is attested once from Messene in Greece in the imperial period. The presumably related name Μήστωρ is slightly more common, and attested once at Selinus in the Archaic period. Μηστρος is presumably therefore not impossible.

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Tréziny, Henry 2018. Mégara Hyblaea. 7, La ville classique, hellénistique et romaine. *CEFR*. Rome. At 206 with fig.311 (dr)

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic4405. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4381912>